

Public data for public good

A report by Involve for the Liverpool Civic Data Co-operative

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Executive Summary

One of the central questions for modern, data driven governments, is how to develop and maintain trustworthy systems of governance for the collection, use and sharing of personal data. The [announcement in January 2020 by the City Region of new plans for a civic data cooperative](#) (CDC) is an exciting development which will pilot a relatively new form of trustworthy data governance. The CDC aims to enable the analysis of anonymised health, social care and civic data for the benefit of the whole city region. If done well, in collaboration with stakeholders and residents across the city region, then it will raise the bar for effective and ethical data governance.

Involve were commissioned to help design and implement a public engagement strategy for the CDC, with an emphasis on citizen participation, clarity, understanding and collaboration.

This report lays out our recommendations and the approach we took to developing them. It takes the ambition and aspiration expressed by the CDC and its stakeholders but also challenges the CDC to be clear on the purpose, and scope of any public engagement.

The risk of presenting the public with a scenario which is too open, and which has no clear purpose or scope, is that they feel further disempowered. In the field of data sharing and consent this is of particular concern; if residents feel that they haven't been given enough detail or the promise of involvement in key decisions isn't real, then they will use the power they have - which is to withdraw consent for their data to be collected and used.

This report assumes a role for the CDC as a transparent actor and communicator to the people of the region about how their data is being collected, analysed, and shared, and of the public health benefits that accrue from that data sharing. To ensure this information is presented in a suitable format for the Liverpool City Region (LCR) residents we also make recommendations about public involvement in the development of these materials. There may also be opportunities for the CDC to develop a wider educational piece about data collection and sharing in general, as well as the specifics of civic data and the CDC.

We then think about the role of the public in the governance and ongoing development of the CDC - primarily as the gateway for researchers to access health and social care data in the LCR and hence as the trusted guardian of access to that data. The recommendations for public engagement and involvement within could be scaled up for use in Cheshire and Merseyside, but with associated resourcing implications.

Overall, we see a role for the CDC as:

- **Informing** the public about how their data is collected and analysed, who can access it, what the approval process is, and the public health benefits that accrue;
- **Involving** the public in approving and designing projects - understanding their motivations and fears and using that information to guide decision-making;
- **Collaborating** with the public to design the governance of the CDC including the role of the public;
- **Networking and learning** so that different publics inform and empower each other in understanding and benefiting from public health data;
- **Demonstrating best practice** in public engagement in the data trust environment.

Involve has been impressed by the commitments the CDC is attempting to make to the people of the Liverpool City Region and we stand ready to assist in developing these aspirations.

Introduction

In January 2020, Liverpool City Region's combined authority [announced new plans for a civic data cooperative](#) (CDC) enabling the analysis of anonymised health, social care and civic data. These plans aimed to join up Liverpool's work in health and social care with its work in the digital and creative sector; seeking to benefit both society and the economy by aligning this work with public and societal expectations through innovative citizen¹ participation and the principles of cooperativism. Since the plan and proposals were announced, the major shifts which were already apparent have accelerated, largely due to the COVID19 pandemic. Of particular note nationally has been the [liberalisation of the sharing of more confidential patient data across the NHS and partner organisations](#), authorised by the Secretary of State for Health. In Cheshire and Merseyside, the pandemic saw the acceleration of the development and use of CIPHA (Combined Intelligence for Population Health Action), a near real-time person level linked dataset across Cheshire and Merseyside. CIPHA enables combined intelligence to be produced that can support population health analytics designed to inform both population level planning and targeting of direct care. The CIPHA Trusted Research Environments (TRE) enable researchers to access CIPHA data.

Involve were commissioned by the CDC to help design and implement a public engagement strategy to support the CDC including in its role as guardian of the CIPHA datasets. The objective is to ensure trustworthy use and sharing of clinical and care data across the region, with an emphasis on citizen participation, clarity, understanding and collaboration. Involve also asked Reema Patel to contribute to the engagement work based on her extensive work on [principles for data stewardship](#)² in her previous role at the Ada Lovelace Institute. This report should be read alongside [the resulting provocation paper](#).³ The paper broadly discusses why a participatory approach to data stewardship is crucial for developing a trustworthy and successful data stewardship model. It examines the notion of membership as implied by the term cooperative and sets out the principles for when data stewards can engage. It also lays out the need for a common and shared purpose to lie behind effective data stewardship. These principles are central to the approach taken in this report.

Our work did not take place in isolation; at the same time [Matchstick Creative](#) were commissioned to develop a marketing strategy, and [Capacity](#) were undertaking engagement work with SMEs in the region to understand how the CDC could add economic value to this sector.

To understand the needs of the CDC in relation to developing a public engagement strategy, we used the framework⁴ developed as a result of Involve's work with the [Open Data Institute](#) to pilot the design of a data trust decision making process for the Greater London Authority and Borough of Greenwich.

¹ The term 'citizen' is used in its widest form and includes anyone who has a clear connection to a place including people experiencing homelessness, asylum seekers and refugees.

² https://www.adalovelaceinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/ADA_Participatory-Data-Stewardship.pdf

³ <https://www.involve.org.uk/sites/default/files/field/attachemnt/Towards%20a%20Civic%20Data%20Cooperative%20in%20Liverpool%20-%20Provocation%20Paper.pdf>

⁴ The original timeline table from the ODI report is included at [Appendix 4](#). Our revised model of proposed decision making for the CDC can be found in [Part 3](#).

Following this model, we began by undertaking a piece of stakeholder engagement with senior figures in and around the CDC.⁵

We undertook a series of interviews, the results of which were synthesised and presented back to interviewees at a facilitated workshop. The workshop also allowed participants to discuss what public engagement might be appropriate at the different points in the life cycle identified below.

We also presented the work to NIHR Applied Research Collaborations (ARC) North West Coast Public Engagement Forum for their feedback. The findings of the stakeholder engagement, feedback from ARC and the report from Reema Patel, together with the results of Matchstick's work and ongoing conversations with the CDC team, have allowed us to develop the recommendations contained in this report. We are grateful for their input.

⁵ A full list of participants and the question framework are provided with the Interview Summary at [Appendix 2](#)

Our approach to public engagement

The first step to ensuring public engagement is useful and effective is to define the purpose and the scope of that engagement. We have chosen to focus our report on two specific areas that we heard were priorities for the CDC. This does not preclude public engagement in other areas.

These two priority areas are for the CDC to:

1. become a transparent and effective communicator about data collection, analysis and the accrued public benefit;
2. act as an ethical and trusted gatekeeper for access to the data.

As noted above, in making our assessment and presenting these recommendations we use the report by Reema Patel as a foundation. This paper identifies many of the fundamental questions that the CDC needs to answer before it can confidently present options for its structure and governance to the public. This includes:

- developing a shared internal understanding of the terminology including *civic*, *cooperative* and *data beneficiaries*;
- making decisions about the geographic scope of the project; and
- defining what it means to embed public engagement in the CDC.

This report takes the ambition and aspiration expressed by the CDC and its stakeholders, but also challenges the CDC to be clear on the purpose, and scope of any public engagement.

The risk of presenting the public with a scenario for the CDC which is too open, without a clear purpose or scope, is that they feel disempowered rather than engaged. In the field of data sharing and consent this is of particular concern; if you open up the conversation, provide information and people feel that they haven't been given enough detail or real power, or that they realise how little power they do have, then they will use the power they have - which in regard to data is to withdraw consent.

This report assumes a role for the CDC as a transparent actor and communicator to the people of the region about how their data is being collected, analysed, and shared, and of the benefits which accrue from that data sharing for public health benefits. To ensure this information is presented in a suitable format for Liverpool City Region (LCR) residents, we also make recommendations about public involvement in developing these materials. There may also be opportunities for the CDC to develop a wider educational piece about data collection and sharing in general, as well as the specifics of civic data and the CDC.

We then think about the role of the public in the governance and ongoing development of the CDC - primarily as the gateway for researchers to access health and social care data in the LCR and hence as the trusted guardian of access to that data, primarily through CIPHA and its TRE but also any other civic datasets that may come under the purview of the CDC. The recommendations for public engagement and involvement could be scaled up for use in Cheshire and Merseyside, but with associated resourcing implications.

We then go on to present areas the public might be involved in, based on the timeline developed with the ODI, and the corresponding points at which coproduction and public engagement can be particularly valuable in the life cycle that are highlighted in Reema Patel's paper:

Before: To help shape and inform the design of the cooperative, working closely with technical and policy stakeholders around scoped and potential options and working models. There must be sufficient information to permit 'intelligent consideration', as well as adequate time to incorporate reflections into the design of the initiative.

During: Institutionalised as part of the mechanisms of the data cooperative itself (this is likely to involve people in how the data itself is curated, collected and used and decisions made by the cooperative) and

After: In enabling data stewards to understand how best to act in ways that use that data effectively, to help aid assessment of how the initiative is working and how it might be able to be improved; and to act as a sense check that the data is being (re)used in the interests of beneficiaries.⁶

We would stress that whilst these are defined moments in the timeline of the CDC, we also see value in a continuous feedback loop that acknowledges a role for the public in evaluating and monitoring the CDC and making recommendations for improvements; most value will be gained from public engagement if it is seen as an iterative rather a wholly linear approach. Our revised version of the ODI framework with our recommended approach for the CDC can be found in [Part 3](#).

⁶ As the Ada Lovelace report '[Participatory Data Stewardship](#)' notes, the term beneficiaries includes 'data subjects', who have a direct relationship with the data in question as specified in the GDPR, and also encompasses those impacted by the use of data (e.g. workers, underrepresented and excluded groups) even if they are not themselves data subjects.

Part 1: What we heard

We interviewed seventeen stakeholders⁷ across different sectors, and the region. We synthesised and themed what we heard in these interviews⁸ and presented the findings to a workshop with 12 participants.

It was clear from the interviews that expectations and aspirations about the CDC were many and broad.

Figure 1: slide presented to stakeholder workshop summarising the purposes for the CDC expressed during interviews

We broke down the interview analysis into three areas of purpose for the CDC and identified key themes in each area:

1. Overall purpose for CDC
 - a. Co-ordinating and improving the efficiency of the civic data system;
 - b. Streamlining access to data sets and breaking down silos - providing for multi-disciplinary teams to work across the system;
 - c. To be an expert and trusted steward of the data;
 - d. To facilitate access to the data - making that access transparent and efficient and improving public involvement; and
 - e. Communicating what access to the data has allowed to be learnt.
2. The purpose of public participation
 - a. To inform the public
 - i. How your data is used and managed;

⁷ A full list of interviewees can be found at [Appendix 2](#)

⁸ The raw data from this exercise is available at [Appendix 2](#)

- ii. The benefits accruing from your data being used - including an educational role so that the public are making informed decisions about data sharing in different contexts; and
 - iii. Feeding back to those collecting, using and sharing data – so that they can understand public preferences or behaviour better, for example.
 - b. To engage the public through co-ordinating, providing and standardising engagement provision
 - c. To empower the public
 - i. By acting as an advocate and strengthening the public voice in how data is used;
 - ii. By acting as a manager of the public voice; and
 - iii. Working with the public to help them identify ways to use data to deal with problems they recognise.
- 3. Long term purposes
 - a. Wealth generation;
 - b. Open data - with the [London Datastore](#) as an example; and
 - c. Improving population health and addressing inequalities in line with the [Sustainable Development Goals](#).

In the workshop, we considered what role the public could play in achieving these objectives. We introduced the spectrum of participation, as adapted for data trusts by the Ada Lovelace Institute.⁹

Figure 2: The spectrum of participation adapted by the Ada Lovelace Institute in [Participatory Data Stewardship](#)

⁹ After presenting this to stakeholders, for the purposes of this report we will be using the term ‘delegate to’ rather than ‘empower’ as the word empower was felt to have different meanings that could be misconstrued.

It was proposed that:

The CDC **should**...

INFORM the public about:

- How data is used
- How data is managed
- The benefits arising from data usage

The CDC **could**...

INVOLVE the public to:

- Understand perspectives, needs and fears
- Inform decisions about data usage

DELEGATE to the public:

- Build networks to share information and experiences relating to the use of and outputs from the data
- Design a public engagement process that meets their needs and the needs of the CDC
- Make decisions
- Identify opportunities

Figure 3: Slide presented to workshop participants outlining the potential purposes for the CDC

Attendees agreed with the proposition that the CDC had a role to inform and indeed educate the public about how their data is collected, processed, managed and shared - and the benefits that have arisen or could arise.

It was clear from the discussion that attendees had the aspiration to fully involve the public, and to delegate some power to them to make decisions about the development and operation of the CDC.

However, precisely how that might happen and if the CDC itself had the capacity or authority to deliver, and what legal constraints there might be around the CDC taking that role, and the limits of the law in what changes any public engagement could affect, was less clear. There was broad agreement that, in order to involve the public in project-based decision making, they would also need to be involved in the design of the CDC from the beginning. Therefore, involving the public in the establishment of the CDC, including asking them the questions about how best to continue and develop the involvement of the public in its governance was felt to be the ideal approach. It was clear that this would involve slowing down, and that the exclusion of the public due to the speed of the response to the pandemic could not become the norm.

In further considering individual data projects attendees saw a real role for the public in decision making. However, establishing principles and rules of engagement and what the public could and couldn't be consulted on was vital. Defining a project, what it meant to the public and what role there

would be for public engagement in designing and in delivering the project will be important. And most critically: How are the CDC and stakeholders going to act upon what the public are advising?

Several key questions emerged from the workshop:

1. Which publics need to be engaged?
2. What is the purpose of engaging the public?
3. Where does the CDC fit in the civic / health infrastructure?
4. What is the geographic scope?

Our recommendations seek to answer the first two of these, but it is outwith our expertise to advise on the latter.

Part 2: A route to public engagement

In this section we explain the importance of establishing a clear purpose before beginning any engagement. We then reflect on the different purposes we have heard for the CDC and the implications this has for the purpose of any engagement the CDC delivers.

Establishing Purpose

What is the objective of the engagement?

Establishing a clear purpose and getting agreement on it is the single most important stage of any engagement process. Indeed, no participatory process should proceed without it.

There are, however, good and bad purposes. A good purpose will be highly focused with clear outputs and outcomes, which are easy for all to understand. A bad purpose will be poorly defined, with unclear outcomes and open to many different interpretations. A measure of a good purpose is its ability to create a commonly shared understanding of the potential impact of the project.

This does not mean that a good purpose must be narrow in its scope. Indeed, many of the best purposes are very broad. The point is that a purpose must be easy to understand and an accurate reflection of what is going to happen. Much of the best participation depends on the participants coming up with their own agenda for change, which is fine, as long as the agenda can then be implemented satisfactorily, and everyone understands what they are part of.

It is essential that all those with an interest or influence over the process are aligned to its purpose. Too often, different purposes exist within the same organisation, sometimes unspoken or assumed, and this only comes to light when the process is underway, which can be both damaging and embarrassing.

Purpose as reference point

Once established, the agreed purpose can provide a reference point throughout the process. This is especially useful if participants are likely to introduce new subjects during the process, as their relevance to the purpose will determine whether they should be included.

A clear purpose enables the commissioning body to ensure that the right mechanisms are in place to transform the process outputs into outcomes. Clarifying the purpose of a process ensures that any organisation knows what it is getting into and can then check whether participation is appropriate.

A purpose also gives participants the opportunity to make an informed choice about getting involved. Too often we hear complaints of people feeling misled or manipulated. This is often because of miscommunication between the commissioner and participants as to what the process can change.

Defining the purpose

Defining a clear purpose is not as easy as it sounds. For an organisation to develop a purpose which is shared by those inside the organisation and any stakeholders which are involved requires time. This is almost always in short supply, especially at the start of a process. External circumstances can also affect the purpose and this possibility should be anticipated. For example, the results of forthcoming research or a decision taken by others can both influence the context and the purpose of

a participation process. This is a particular risk if the process is not recognised or valued by people more senior than those involved in the detailed design and delivery.

It is important that defining the purpose includes clarity about the desired outputs and outcomes. Outcomes are about what you ultimately want to achieve (for example, consensus on which uses of data should be permitted and which not); outputs are how you will achieve the outcomes (for example, a report including recommendations from participants). Making the distinction clear will contribute to defining a robust and useful purpose.

In summary, there are many possible purposes for participation, including to:

- Inform about defined activities;
- Educate about the wider context - how data is used, who uses it for what purpose, the benefits it can have and how the data is protected etc;
- Network and share ideas;
- Make a decision; and
- Explore issues and come up with new ideas.

In addition, organisations may have in mind the core participation purposes identified above (governance, social cohesion and social justice, improved quality of services, capacity building and learning).

Identifying such purposes will involve:

- Liaising internally to clarify what can be changed as a result of the process and what outputs and outcomes are sought.
- Liaising externally with those affected by a process to identify people's interests and concerns.

The key questions to help clarify the purposes of the exercise will be:

- What tangible products do you want to have produced during and after the process (outputs)?
- What do you want to have achieved at the end of this process (outcomes)?

And a checking question:

- What will you have to do with the outputs to ensure you achieve the desired outcomes?

Our sense of your purpose(s)

It has become clear that the CDC in fact has multiple purposes which public engagement could help meet. This is largely due to the different stages in the life cycle where engagement could take place.

The table identifies a number of purposes which the CDC could use to define its public engagement.

Purpose	Outputs	Outcomes
Informing the public about how their data is collected and analysed, who can access it, what the approval process is, and the public health benefits that accrue.	Stakeholder events Communications public panel Materials Public events (led by trusted stakeholders)	Knowledge of and trust in the CDC Willingness to engage more deeply
Involving the public in approving and designing projects - understanding their motivations and fears and using that information to guide decision-making.	Any access requests either meet pre-agreed criteria defined by a mini-public or are themselves tested with a mini-public	Needs and fears are better understood, informing decisions that cannot involve the public (eg for reasons of speed)
Collaborating with the public to design the governance of the CDC including the role of the public.	A role for a public panel alongside any other governance structures to monitor and inform	The CDC sets a gold standard for public engagement and involvement and demonstrates trustworthiness
Networking and learning so that different publics inform and empower each other in understanding and benefiting from public health data.	Ongoing evidence to and feedback from public panels, mini-publics, stakeholder groups and the public	Trusted relationships between data holders, data subjects and data users ensure better public health outcomes and shared understanding of risks and benefits of public data for public good
To demonstrate best practice in public engagement in the data trust environment.	Transparent and communicable governance and practice standards	A community of practice appreciates a gold standard of public involvement, ensuring an environment of trustworthiness

Each of the purposes for the CDC identified above implies different reasons for engaging the public. While these are not mutually exclusive, the CDC has limited resources for public engagement. Choices and priorities need to be agreed before the CDC can effectively engage the public.

Scope - who do you want to engage with?

1. What is open to change (and what is not)?

Defining the scope of any engagement in the CDC involves clarifying what the boundaries are, what is achievable in practice – and whether engagement is appropriate at all. This allows you to begin to determine what level of engagement is right for your purpose

In order to effectively engage, in a way that adds value to both the CDC and the public, it is necessary that:

- The public can influence, to some degree, the decisions they are being invited to engage on
- The public participation will bring in something new
- The public are interested in being involved
- There are sufficient resources to support the process and ensure it works properly

Understanding what you can offer and why leads to your 'promise to the public'.

Figure 4: what is open to change

With this in mind, we have identified what we think can change for each of the identified purposes, and therefore what your promise to the public is.

Purpose	What could change?	What can't change?	Your promise to the public
<p>Informing the public about how their data is collected and analysed, who can access it, what the approval process is, and the public health benefits that accrue.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Target groups ● Content of materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The data collection ● Access to the data 	<p>We will communicate accessible, timely and accurate information about the work of the CDC</p>
<p>Involving the public in approving and designing projects - understanding their motivations and fears and using that information to guide decision-making.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Amendments to project design ● Comms about the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No public veto - a collaborative approach ● Who proposes the project(?) 	<p>You can help us shape the projects we deliver using your data. We commit to explaining to you if and how you have had an impact on the project</p>
<p>I) Collaborating with the public to design and deliver the governance of the CDC including the role of the public.</p> <p>II) Collaborating with the public to design and deliver data projects</p>	<p>Level I</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who is involved in governance? ● The structure and purpose of governance structure ● Key decisions including potential contribution to veto <p>Level II</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Shape and structure of data projects ● Proposal for projects ● Potential veto over projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Decisions subject to legal restrictions <p>(There will also be a set of decisions that are guided by partner requirements, funding stipulations etc where you will need to clearly articulate the scope for change)</p>	<p>If you decide to involve the public in design of the governance structure and then within this you will be promising:</p> <p>Level I: You will have a clearly defined role within the design and delivery of the governance of the CDC including the power to shape decisions.</p> <p>Level II: We will work with you to design and deliver data projects that meet your needs</p>

Purpose	What could change?	What can't change?	Your promise to the public
<p>Networking and learning so that different stakeholders and the public inform and empower each other in understanding and benefiting from public health data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who finds out about the project and how? • Who is at the table 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decisions subject to legal requirements including privacy. • The scope of the projects (this is a reporting and learning stage, not a decision making stage). 	<p>We will facilitate conversations between the public and different stakeholder groups so that you have an informed understanding of how your data is being used, and that stakeholders have an understanding of your priorities.</p>
<p>To demonstrate best practice in public engagement in the data stewardship environment.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Membership of the network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decisions subject to legal requirements including privacy. • The scope of the projects (this is a reporting and learning stage, not a decision making stage). 	<p>We will share what we learn from you with others in the sector to ensure our learning is cyclical and embedded across data actors.</p>

Once purpose and scope have been identified, the final questions start thinking about methods. Which method can best achieve the purpose within the scope without exacerbating risk and in a cost effective manner:

1. How might you involve the public in order to achieve the purpose and when?
2. What are the risks which could be mitigated by effective public engagement / might be exacerbated by ineffective public engagement?
3. What level of expenditure on engagement is proportionate given the possibility for change and the risks identified? (Cost / Benefit)

Part 3: How to develop and embed public engagement in the CDC

Who needs to be involved?

The use of civic data for civic outcomes brings with it a wide range of stakeholders as well as the public. We would suggest that stakeholder groups be considered as a complementary part of public engagement, and that the CDC seek to embed cross-fertilisation between stakeholders and the public.

Our overarching suggestion for how the CDC might approach public engagement is to take a staged approach which will progressively become more embedded in the decision making processes of the CDC. This will allow the engagement with the public to move from 'Inform' to something deeper. In taking a staged approach, how much decision making is devolved can be assessed at each stage to ensure efficiency, effectiveness, and appropriateness. We believe this will allow the CDC to better understand the needs of the public and their interest in engaging as well as providing for the development of trust between the public and the CDC as you progressively delegate more of the decision making.

This approach will involve embedding public engagement in different communities (of place and of interest) across the city region, so could be scaled up to Cheshire & Merseyside if desired. This approach aims to also develop ties within and between communities and to ensure that the CDC is both utilising and supporting existing networks.

Our rationale for this approach is as follows:

Purpose

Your purposes are diverse and depend on the stage in the life cycle of the engagement and the public(s) you wish to engage with. Our approach seeks to build from the fundamental purpose of informing the public about how their data is used and the benefits that accrue. We feel building in this way will help avoid misunderstanding and disappointment about the role of the public. It will also demonstrate trustworthiness.

Publics

Your publics are also varied, and will have different incentives for participating, and different levels of influence. Our proposed approach seeks to embed cross-fertilisation across your publics, so they are informing and empowering each other as well as contributing to the development of an ethical and transparent CDC.

Scope

The scope of the engagement and the promise to the public varies depending on the level of decision making that is possible to be devolved. In some areas of the CDC operation the public will be able to have a stronger influence than in others. Our proposed approach allows you to be clear where change

is possible, and where it is not, enabling you to answer the following questions about the purpose of the engagement:

- Is it to invite the public to inform decision making? To what extent?
- Is it to invite the public to 'authorise' (or refuse) something?
- Is it to find out the public's thinking on the trade-offs around ethics and public good?

It is also intended to deliver a transparent CDC which we believe will help you build an engaged audience who will want to participate. Effective public engagement requires your public(s) to want to be engaged.

Our approach also acknowledges that there is much that is not open to change. It seeks to provide a growing role for the public in the work of the CDC, such that the public understand the aspirations for their involvement, but also its limitations. It provides for strengthening feedback loops within and across the public and stakeholder groups so that as the engagement becomes more collaborative it remains fit for purpose for the CDC, stakeholders, and the public.

Our proposed methods¹⁰ for this approach.

This approach aims to build engagement from the bottom up. The final stages will require the CDC to choose between developing a way of engaging in some areas which currently are not open to change or deciding to limit the involvement of the public in order to ensure that they are not asked to make recommendations which subsequently have to be declined. We would suggest that co-creation and a full public voice is a more sustainable approach which is more likely to build trust over the long term.

1. *A community conversation with communities of interest and / or place, including stakeholder groups.*

Aim: to ensure the principles of the CDC are fit for purpose and that all communications about the CDC are useful, accessible, and understandable across a wide variety of demographics and stakeholders.

Methodology: A community conversation methodology would partner with groups and organisations with existing networks. This could include:

- Providing resources and support for organisations to host their own conversations and provide an appropriate honorarium to participants to support their participation;
- Developing a pack to guide community hosts through the process, including a common conversation guide and options for different ways they might run the conversation tasks including online and face to face, together with an introductory PowerPoint presentation;
- Providing support for engaging different groups, such as:
 - Resourcing to provide British Sign Language translation and live captioning;
 - Alternative text simple picture descriptions (Alt Text) and fuller picture descriptions for the presentations;
 - Providing the presentation in different formats – e.g., large text and printed versions for visually impaired participants; and
 - The offer of translation into Easy Read format.

¹⁰ More information about different methodologies can be found on the Involve website <https://www.involve.org.uk/resources/methods>

- Providing a common feedback mechanism to collate the results from the conversations.

2. *An iterative development of people's panels that widen the community conversation to additional operational and decision making aspects of the CDC, including developing requirements for data access and whether that access should be contingent on public engagement within research projects.*

Aim: to begin to offer representative public involvement in setting the engagement standards for the CDC.

Methodology: This would involve the participation of a representative sample of the public which would be engaged in a deliberative process that would seek to develop and extend the community conversations. There would be a number of dialogues across the region over a period of months. This would build a picture of the aspirations of the public for the CDC and their role within it.

3. *Representatives from the panels and communities come together to decide the terms of a standing mini public which will act alongside any ethics / access committees of the CDC. These committees should be regularly and continually testing their approach with the group.*

Aim: to ensure the voice of the public is heard at all levels of governance and decision making within the CDC

Methodology: The precise method used to co-create this mini public will be decided by the representatives.

4. *The board (or other governance committee), any ethics and / or access committees will report regularly to the representative group and will receive updates from the group.*

Aim: to maintain lines of communication between levels of governance and the public.

Methodology: The precise method used for reporting will be decided by the group.

5. *The representative group will be responsible for reporting back and seeking feedback from the panels and communities.*

Aim: to keep the information flowing to all levels of the community and back to the centre.

Methodology: The precise method used for reporting will be decided by the group.

6. *As the knowledge and interest of the public grows, the CDC could consider commissioning a citizens' assembly to bring together a cross section of the region to review the operation of the CDC and make recommendations as to the future approach. It is suggested the assembly be asked to consider how best the Liverpool City region can use public data to improve public health outcomes and address inequality (with a view to meeting the SDGs).*

Aim: to publicly and fairly have a conversation with the region about the role of data in public health outcomes and tackling inequality in order that:

- i. The public understand and see the value in data sharing and research access to that data; and
- ii. Decisions about data sharing do not have unforeseen consequences that damage public health, increase inequality, and decrease trust.

Methodology: Best practice suggests that the design of a citizen's assembly should be a co-production process, with the stakeholders identified by a steering group. It is also possible to include members of the assembly in this process. Below we propose a potential wider public engagement to establish the remit and design of the assembly.

6.1 The citizens assembly's remit and design will be determined by the public in a facilitated workshop that is broadly representative of the panels and communities. It should be permitted to include consideration of the role of the public in:

- a. Setting research priorities;
- b. Approving research proposals;
- c. Establishing criteria for access to the data;
- d. Contributing to requirements for public engagement within research projects
- e. Initiating research proposals;
- f. Designing the communication about research - as it happens and any outputs and outcomes;
- g. Suggesting areas for increased funding or attention from the CDC (ie identifying calls for research interest as well as reacting to incoming proposals); and
- h. Identifying unintended consequences of research and suggesting mitigation strategies

Alternatively, you could skip straight to the citizens' assembly, but the risk is that without having done the groundwork with communities you do not stimulate interest. Aside from potentially impacting participation in the assembly itself, this would mean that the work of the assembly risks going under the radar and therefore being easy to dismiss. It would also mean that the stated aim of including all Liverpool Region residents in the CDC would be harder to achieve.

The CDC could reconvene a refreshed assembly annually or bi-annually to reflect on the work of the CDC and to hear from the panels (also regularly refreshed) established in 1-5. As time went on this could take the role of an AGM, with residence in the city region gifting membership of the CDC and the right to apply for membership of any of the public engagement processes.

Alongside this, a complementary piece of work with the identified communities of interest would seek to ensure that under-represented and easy to ignore groups were supported to both contribute through trusted intermediaries from inside the spaces where they felt comfortable and to be encouraged to participate in the wider engagement processes, with appropriate support, mentoring and pastoral care.

Additionally, the CDC could develop a pilot study or studies utilising either an existing research cohort - like C-GULL (a birth cohort study tracing the lives of over 10,000 Liverpudlians to understand more about what influences the health and wellbeing of children and their families living in the region), or by introducing the digital twin concept. However, we would suggest these are seen as additional defined projects within the overall approach. This would enable the CDC to test what sort of project level engagement might be possible.

Finally, the CDC should consider if it has a role in delivering wider education about data collection, processing, management and sharing. Certainly, by instigating transparent and effective communication about its own work, the CDC could demonstrate best practice about what the public should expect from those who seek to access their data. Equally, individual projects or pilots could be used as a wider educational tool by demonstrating principles, approaches and recommended public

actions that could be applicable across the data stewardship environment and not just in the context of civic data.¹¹

¹¹ Here we are imagining that, for example, in empowering the public to understand what happens to their data in the process of consenting to share it for civic purposes, the CDC could also offer guidance on how to interpret and apply cookie consents and other common data trawling tools.

An overview of the proposed decision making process, adapted from the [model involve developed with the ODI](#), revised to reflect our recommendations above.

OVERVIEW MODEL OF PROPOSED DECISION-MAKING PROCESS FOR LIVERPOOL CIVIC DATA COOPERATIVE							
>>> Timeline of key decisions >>>							
1. Data Coop Formation & Design Decisions (Before)			2. Operational Decisions (During)		3. Exceptional Decisions (After)		
	Decisions on formation, design, function, and approach to decision-making	What governing and core operating principles should the coop have?	What criteria used to decide who has access to the data and under what conditions?	Decisions on granting access from the data coop	How is performance against purpose, principles, and values?	Edge cases (i.e. those which fall outside the pre-defined parameters)	What happens if the coop fails?
Purpose of engagement/ deliberative engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * To gain buy into the overall purpose and approach of the coop. * To agree the framing of the coop - who it is driven by and who it is for? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Build ownership amongst stakeholders at the outset. * Understand expectations of stakeholders/ public * Understand where trade-offs may be around data use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Build agreement on the criteria. * Build trust that data shared for, reflecting public hopes and fears. * Gain insight into how people judge outcomes from data use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Whether access is granted and under what conditions using the agreed criteria. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * To understand whether the trust is meeting expectations and if not, why? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * To review for cases challenging criteria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * What happens to the data accrued? What happens to the benefits accrued?
Who needs to be involved 	Funders, commissioners, Emergent data stewards; legal input	Emergent data stewards; legal input, wider stakeholders, public	Emergent data stewards; legal input, wider stakeholders, public	Data stewards, stakeholders, public	Data stewards, stakeholders, public	Expert views (e.g. legal); Representation of key stakeholders.	Expert views (e.g. legal); Representation of key stakeholders.
Through what process 	Facilitated stakeholder workshop(s) to make decisions	Community Conversations (including stakeholder groups) Public Panels	Standing mini-public established to act alongside CDC board and / or ethics committee / access committee with reps from CC and PP	Standing mini-public and CDC governance committees develop feedback loops with regular two-way reporting	Possible public involvement in individual projects	Citizen jury or assembly feeding back to panel	Citizen jury or assembly feeding back to panel
	Core group helps co-design deliberative elements	Outreach to underrepresented groups Online engagement?	Standing mini public acts as a touchstone and oversight of data coop operations				

Figure 5: Overview of decision making process for Liverpool CDC

Part 4: The CDC in 2032

As public engagement becomes embedded and normalised, we envisage the CDC moving from a series of interlocking and cross-pollinating groups to an organisation with the public voice at its heart. The structures of the CDC would be democratic, transparent, and accountable.

2023

If the approach we recommend above is implemented, we envision a number of complementary activities feeding in to and back towards each other, whilst also embedding a core structure centred on the Board, Ethics Committee and the representative mini-public, with an overlapping membership and co-operative relationship.

Figure 6: Potential model of the connections between public engagement and governance in 2023

2024

As the CDC develops, this core structure will be able to commission a Citizens Assembly to test current ways of working and discuss the future of the CDC, including ongoing, deepening, and embedding public participation.

Figure 7: The next iteration of the public engagement – governance model is 2024

2032

Finally, one of the possible outcomes of this ongoing collaboration could be that the core structure remains, with mechanisms for membership open to all members of the co-operative (and membership of the co-operative open to all residents of the region), and accountability being met through an AGM.

Figure 8: A potential end point for the public engagement governance model in 2032

Part 5: A Final Recommendation

The role of data in improving civic outcomes is growing exponentially. How data is collected, used, analysed, and shared is complicated and can be opaque. Poorly explained or overly technical methods of providing 'choice' for the public are prevalent. As our lives become increasingly governed by what data says about us, it is vital that the public not only are informed about how data about them is collected, analysed, and shared, but that they actively understand the implications and are able to participate in decision making, and possibly shape how the data is managed and used.

The growth of data trusts and data co-operatives, and their ambitions to demonstrate the public good that well managed data can deliver, as well as a desire to include the public in understanding trade-offs and making decisions around data collection, analysis and sharing is generating many different models and approaches.

Therefore, our final recommendation to the CDC is that it seeks to establish a Community of Practice around the role of the public in data stewardship and the use of civic data. The collection, management and use of data is changing and growing incredibly quickly. If we are to best understand how to act ethically and in the public interest; take the public with us; and delegate decisions to them about how data is managed, it is vital we learn from each other as well as testing our assumptions with our data subjects.

Involve has been impressed by the commitments the CDC is attempting to make to the people of the Liverpool City Region and we stand ready to assist in developing these aspirations.

Appendix 1: About Involve

Who we are

We're the UK's leading public participation charity, on a mission to put people at the heart of decision-making.

We're a small but passionate team focused on giving people more power over the decisions that affect their lives. We want to build a stronger democracy that works for everyone – that gives people real power to bring about change in their lives, communities and beyond.

Involve was founded in 2003 to “to create a new focus for thinking and action on the links between new forms of public participation and existing democratic institutions”. We've been promoting and practising participatory and deliberative decision-making ever since. We have worked with governments, parliaments, civil society organisations, academics and the public across the UK and internationally to put people at the heart of decision-making.

We believe that decision-making in the UK needs to be more:

- **Open** - so that people can understand, influence and hold decision-makers to account for the actions and inactions of their governments;
- **Participatory** - so that people have the freedom, support and opportunity to shape their communities and influence the decisions that affect their lives; and,
- **Deliberative** - so that people can exchange and acknowledge different perspectives, understand conflict and find common ground, and build a shared vision for society.

What we do

We demonstrate how citizens can help solve our biggest challenges.

Democracy isn't working as it should. Decision-makers are struggling to get things done. The public are frustrated that the system isn't working for them. And everywhere people are feeling divided, distrustful and powerless.

Our work seeks to create:

1. **New innovations** - to demonstrate better ways of doing democracy;
2. **New institutions** - to put people at the heart of decision-making;
3. **New norms** - to make democracy more open, participatory and deliberative.

We approach this in three ways:

1. **We set the agenda** - by developing a vision of a democracy that puts people at the heart of decision-making;
2. **We build coalitions** - by mobilising and partnering with broad, unexpected and powerful networks of allies; and,
3. **We make it happen** - by developing and supporting world-class participatory and deliberative processes.

Our recent projects have included:

- **Scotland's Climate Assembly** - the first online only citizens' assembly in Scotland charged with answering the question: How can Scotland table the climate emergency in a fair and effective way?;
- **NHS Test and Trace Public Advisory Group** - Between May and June 2021, the NHS Test and Trace Public Advisory Group brought together people from different backgrounds to inform new policies to help England come out of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic;
- **Developing a citizen led Data Charter in Camden** - working with the Council to develop a deliberative process to create a Data Charter to guide the Council's decisions about the conditions under which it should collect, analyse, share and use data to inform policy, research and service delivery. Our work consisted of two components: - a distributed dialogue and a citizens' jury.
- Find out more about our work: www.involve.org.uk/our-work/

Our values

- **Collaboration** – because change comes when broad coalitions of people work towards a common vision.
- **Equality** – because everyone in society has an equal right to be listened to and participate in decisions that affect their lives. No one should be held back by societal divisions or prejudice.
- **Purpose** – because participation must have an impact. We reject tokenistic or ineffectual engagement.

Appendix 2: Interview Summary

Interviewees

- Iain Buchan
- Helen Duckworth
- Jim Hughes
- Tony Marsden
- John Whaling
- Andy Mills
- Paul Charnley
- Matt Ashton
- Amanda Lamb
- Ian Pawson
- Claire Liddy
- William Hope
- Drew Hill
- Maurice Smith
- Janet Jennings
- Rob Barnett
- Alex Chaplin

Question framework¹²

Questions about their role and data

- Can you tell us a little about your role, and specifically how you use and share data?

Questions about the CDC and its role

- What role will the CDC play within the data sharing infrastructure in the city region?
- What benefits will it bring?
- What friction will it bring to the system? How can this be minimised?
- Who are the key actors in the system who need to be part of the CDC to make it worthwhile?/ What key datasets does the CDC need to hold? Why these?
 - do they see the benefits in the same way?
- What does success look like for you? How will you know if the CDC is working?
- [if time] Why a coop and not some other governance structure?
- Problem of scale - how to get the region as a whole to participate and feel a sense of ownership? Engagement with hard to reach people and communities?

Questions about public engagement and its role

- A key element of the CDC is involving the public. What role do you think the public have within the CDC?

¹² This framework was used as a basis for all the interviews, however, not all interviewees were asked all questions, and the priority given to the question sets varied according to the role of the interviewee.

- What are your objectives for public engagement in relation to:
 - The establishment of the CDC?
 - The governance of the CDC - what should it's governance look like?
 - The use of data and public health (NHS, local government, other orgs, existing groups)?
- What public engagement around data has already taken place in Liverpool and Merseyside on data and its governance?
- Again, what does good look like in terms of public engagement process and outcome?
- Another way of asking these questions, what are the areas of risk that might reduce public trust and public engagement through the co-op could reduce? What decisions keep you awake at night? How might the CDC help you address those fears?

Synthesis of the interviews

The jamboard slides below show the themes that developed from our synthesis of the interviews.

Figure 9: Theming of what we heard in the interviews around the overall purpose of the CDC

Figure 10: Theming of what we heard in the interviews around the purpose of public participation in the CDC

Figure 11: Theming of what we heard in the interviews around the long term aims of the CDC

Figure 12: Opportunities for public engagement identified by interviewees

Appendix 3: Workshop Summary

Attendees

- Helen Duckworth
- Iain Buchan
- Rob Barnett
- John Whaling
- William Hope
- Lisa A’Hearne
- Gary Leeming
- Emma Lord
- Claire Smith
- Jim Hughes
- Amanda Lamb
- Andy Mills
- Saah Wright
- Angela Johnson
- Reema Patel
- Greg Macoy
- Ellie Fielding

Liverpool Civic Data Co-op

The role of the public

Why create the CDC?

Harnessing data's value for economic and social benefit needs:

- public trust
- data to be available to those who need it

To be effective decisions need to be made about:

- who should have access
- for what purposes
- for whose benefit
- the role of the public

CDC is at the forefront of the debate about data stewardship

Changing context ... adapting purpose?

Evolution of form as it has developed

- Trust or Co-operative

The pandemic

- Covid and CIPHA

Wider governance reforms

- Integrated Care Systems

Expectations are many and broad

- And deliver with a team of ten people... And no official authority... And limited resources

Emerging consensus about core functions

Facilitation not IG

- Open data
- Processes for accessing closed data (in partnership with CIPHA)
- Identifying value
 - Public support, ethical status, benchmarking
 - Cross-sector consortia (including industry) to solve wicked problems
 - Sustainable Development Goals

The public are critical, but what is their role?

The role of the public – different perspectives

The CDC must ...

INFORM the public about:

- how data is used
- how data is managed
- the benefits arising from data usage

The CDC could ...

INVOLVE the public to:

- understand perspectives, needs, hopes and fears
- inform decisions about data usage

EMPOWER the public to:

- use data
- make decisions
- identify opportunities

The role of the public – in what?

Three different options

- In the formation of the CDC
- In the governance of the CDC
- In the development and delivery of individual data projects

When: Developing the CDC

Question: “What legal form should the CDC take and what conditions should be placed on who it should and shouldn’t work with, and how should it prioritise projects?”

Who: A citizens’ assembly, formed of a large representative sample could be presented with evidence and given time to deliberate

Outcomes:

Involve: Recommendations considered, responded to but not necessarily implemented.

Empower: co-creating the governance and the mechanisms for permitting access and project prioritisation

When: In the governance of the CDC

Question: What key principles should be applied in the governance framework of the CDC, including how it makes decisions about access to datasets and prioritisation of projects?

Who: A People’s Panel of a smaller representative sample meeting regularly both to discuss data access requests

Outcomes:

Involve: Panel comments on data access requests against agreed principles, these are considered, but may not be implemented

Empower: Panel can veto data access requests

When: Project by project

Question: *How can we ensure individual data projects meet the needs of residents?*

Who: Using a distributed dialogue process, community groups are engaged to consider individual projects

Outcomes:

Involve: Residents provide input into their perspectives on the problem and potential solutions, these taken into account as data project delivered

Empower: Residents involved in scoping projects and making key decisions about research questions and decisions based on findings

In your groups

Consider at least two of the options

1. What level of public engagement is appropriate for this option? Why?
2. What would you need to see to give you confidence to act on what the public says?
3. Is this a priority area for CDC to invest in engaging the public? Why?
4. Does the CDC have the authority to offer the level of engagement proposed? If not, should it have it?

Report from workshop

The Liverpool Civic Data Cooperative (CDC) was introduced in 2020 with a view to being a trusted third party to facilitate research access to health and social care data in the Liverpool City Region (LCR).

Involve was commissioned in 2021 to work with the CDC to advise on the public engagement needed as part of the process to design the CDC as well as the ongoing engagement likely to be needed.

The first stage of our work involved interviewing key stakeholders across the LCR.

The stakeholder workshop was the second phase of our work seeking to understand how best to engage the public in the Liverpool Civic Data Cooperative. It involved a number of the stakeholder interviewees from across different sections of the infrastructure within which the CDC seeks to operate.

The main purpose of the workshop was to explore what level of engagement attendees thought was most appropriate, and at what stage of the development / operation of the CDC.

The specified objectives were:

1. To develop a shared understanding of the role of Liverpool City Region residents within the CDC
2. To develop options for public engagement within the CDC

After a short presentation from Simon Burall and a Q&A, attendees discussed in small groups at what level the public might be engaged at each defined stage of the CDC's development and operation.

It was clear from the discussion that attendees had the aspiration to fully involve the public, and to hand over some power to them to make decisions about the development and operation of the CDC.

This is a cooperative approach so any individual or any member of the network could have an actionable idea.

However, precisely how that might happen and if the CDC itself had the capacity, authority, or legal standing to make it happen remained unconfirmed. This brief report seeks to provide an overview of the discussions.

The role of the public

Based on Involve's previous work, including with the ODI, we identified three moments when the CDC might choose to engage the public - at each moment that could be at the perspective of 'inform', 'involve' or 'empower'.

It is clear from the nomenclature that the CDC should include the public voice to some degree.

Coop means involving the public. structure. But there do have to be appropriate controls to manage that whilst also maintaining transparency. It will be important to have methods to empower and involve the public.

At minimum the public wants to be informed and have a say around that.

Cooperative implies putting some power into the hands of the public.

It was also evident from the discussion that to do this will mean giving the CDC the time and capacity to implement effective processes.

If we really want to do this, we have to slow down decision making processes, think about how the public will add value and how to reach out to them.

However, it was less clear what the purpose and scope of the public's involvement would be.

Also, the question of why are we doing it? We're looking to get public opinion but also to educate.

We want to explain to people what we do with data. Question is how much do we act on the opinions we hear. That is quite different. And in any one room there will be a spread of views. Maybe it is about getting the tone – there will be a spectrum of opinions.

We need to define what the scope might be – involve and empower – answers might be different depending on where applied – e.g. ICS/NHS obligations to use data in a certain way/treat patients/improve services. We can't change the COPI notice but we can surface opinions and inform people why we cannot do these things.

We also heard that there were challenges in the authority the CDC would have to act on what it heard from the public, and that it was being asked to navigate a complex array of brokers.

CDC doesn't have authority to take decisions on data. It has authority to raise the profile of data and start the debate/ ask questions on what data can do for unheard communities or people with particular conditions. Groups across the NHS and the local authority need to come together in a coop to have integrated governance to better serve our communities.

Original point that if we do this, will set expectations and we haven't got legitimacy therefore set up to fail if we don't set parameters in advance within the legal framework – need to understand this. Empower **and** set the scope.

From Involve's perspective, given the creation of the CDC, and the use of the word 'cooperative', it seems clear that the intention was that at the very least the CDC would seek to 'inform' the people of the Liverpool City Region about how their data is used and managed, and the benefits that accrue to the region from the ways the data is used.

The risk facing the CDC is that if you open up the conversation, provide information and people feel that they haven't been given real power or that they realise how little power they do have, then they will use the power they have - which in regard to data is to withdraw consent.

It is therefore vital that the CDC understands what it can offer the public before it begins to engage. The purpose and scope of any engagement must be clear. In this respect the workshop raised more questions than answers.

Issues identified by participants

1. Who is the public?

Questions that were raised during the workshop included what the definition of 'public(s)' includes - and this is important to understand. The CDC will need to engage different publics, from institutional stakeholders and GPs to community representatives and elected officials, as well as the general

public. And of course, in any given instance each individual will in fact be representative of several different publics. The question is whether the CDC has the capacity to coordinate across such a wide range of actors. There are also challenges in reaching under-represented groups - this would require specific resourcing.

Next steps: The CDC team needs to identify its priority audiences and why it needs to engage them.

2. Where does the CDC fit in the civic / health infrastructure?

Concerns were raised about both the legal identity of the CDC and how it fits into the existing frameworks in the region. The CDC is attempting to work across both democratic and civic infrastructures and the complex infrastructure of the health and social care system, including the medicalised approach taken by the NHS.

Next steps: Working with its key stakeholders, the CDC team needs to identify its role within the civic/ health infrastructure. One way of doing this is to more clearly identify the value it will bring to the system.

In order to assist the CDC team, these key stakeholders need to decide what power, if any, they are willing to share with the CDC.

3. What is the geographic scope?

This leads on to another aspect of the discussion which questioned the geographic scope of the CDC. CDC is funded by LCR but clearly the health system is larger than that and it might be desirable to work at a Cheshire and Merseyside scale. However, the discussion also included the value of working at a PLACE level, understanding the hyper local needs of communities. The benefits of establishing the CDC as a local / sub-regional player to challenge the trend towards centralisation was noted.

Next steps: The CDC team and its key stakeholders have a number of options for the geographic footprint of the CDC. It will be tempting to try to operate within different geographic scales. However, this will make the decisions needed around purpose (see below), much more challenging. It will be more effective to identify a clear focus and grown from there over time. A decision needs to be made about the geographic scope - and how that fits into the national conversation and a trend towards centralisation.

4. What is the purpose of engaging the public?

As identified above, there was a lack of consensus on the purpose of engaging the public, including a conversation about trustworthiness and the extent to which engaging the public can help with this.

Next steps: The CDC needs to be clear on why it is seeking to engage the public and to what extent. Without a clear understanding of why you want to involve the public you cannot be clear on the offer you are making to them.

Conclusions

Overall, attendees acknowledged that information provision was a critical element in the role of CDC. It was also proposed that in order to have the public involved in project-based decision making, they would need to be involved in the design of the CDC from the beginning. They would need to be the ones deciding who was asked what and when. Involving the public in the establishment of the CDC, including asking them the questions about how best to involve the public in its governance would be

the ideal approach. It was clear that this would involve slowing down, and that the exclusion of the public in the speed of the response to the pandemic could not become the norm.

In considering individual data projects attendees saw a real role for the public in decision making. However, establishing principles and rules of engagement and what the public could and couldn't be consulted on was vital. Defining a project and what it meant to the public would be of importance, is a project collecting data in CIPHA or doing something additional with the data? And, of utmost importance: How are you going to act upon what the public are advising?

We must not lose the ambition to empower but need to do it slowly. There is room for it but it is difficult e.g if we empower patient care it would be framed differently – ask people on waiting lists 'what will you do' – this is potentially disruptive to the NHS but could save lives and reduce costs.

Appendix 4: ODI model timeline

Overview model of proposed decision-making processes for a data trust - Taken from Involve (2019) [Greater London Authority/Royal Borough of Greenwich data trust pilot: Design of a decision-making process](#)

1. Data Trust Formation & Design Decisions				>>> Timeline of key decisions >>>		3. Exceptional Decisions	
2. Operational Decisions							
	Decisions on formation, design, function and approach to decision-making	What governing and core operating principles should this trust have?	What criteria used to decide who has access to the data and under what conditions?	Decisions on granting access from the data trust	How is performance against purpose, principles and values?	Edge cases	What happens if the trust fails?
Purpose of engagement/deliberative engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To gain buy into the overall purpose and approach of the trust. To agree the framing of the trust - who it is driven by and who it is for? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build ownership amongst stakeholders at the outset. Understand expectations of stakeholders/ public Understand where trade-offs may be around data use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build agreement on the criteria. Build trust that data shared for, reflecting public hopes and fears. Gain insight into how people judge outcomes from data use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Whether access is granted and under what conditions using the agreed criteria. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To understand whether the trust is meeting expectations and if not, why? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To review for cases challenging criteria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What happens to the data accrued? What happens to the benefits accrued?
Who needs to be involved 	Funders, commissioners, Emergent data steward; legal input	Emergent data steward/ trustees; legal input, wider stakeholders, public	Emergent data steward/trustee; legal input, wider stakeholders, public	Data steward/ trustees, stakeholders, public	Data steward/trustees, stakeholders, public	Expert views (e.g. legal); Representation of key stakeholders.	Expert views (e.g. legal); Representation of key stakeholders.
Through what process 	Facilitated workshop(s) to make decisions	Core stakeholder group co-production process		Stakeholder/ public reference panel input	Review by stakeholder public/ reference panel; Mini public/ citizen jury or assembly feeding back to reference panel	Review by stakeholder /public reference panel; Mini public/ citizen jury or assembly feeding back to reference panel	Review by stakeholder /public reference panel;
	Core group helps co-design deliberative elements	Outreach to underrepresented groups Online engagement?					
			Establish public /stakeholder reference panel as a touchstone and oversight of data trust				